

Fighting Antipsychotic-Induced Obesity Using a Common-Sense Approach

Gabriel A. Fernandez, DNP, RN, PMHP-BC Jill Berg, PhD, RN Dana N. Rutledge, PhD, RN

Background

- People suffering from severe mental illness have high prevalence of obesity
- Antipsychotic use may lead to ↑weight and ↓metabolic health. Long-term antipsychotic use → ↓quality of life and ↑risk for premature mortality
- Leventhal's CSM has been used successfully to frame behavioral interventions

Local Context

- Approximately 50 patients in a fast-paced community clinic are taking antipsychotic medication; most are overweight/obese
- No structured healthy lifestyle education/counseling is done during provider visits

Project Purpose

- To develop, implement, and evaluate a patient-centered intervention based on the CSM to promote healthy lifestyle behaviors
- Long-term goal is to ↓weight of overweight/obese mentally ill individuals taking antipsychotic medications

Methods

- Project implemented during 20 minute monthly medication follow-up visits with a psychiatric nurse practitioner (PNP)
- 5-minute discussion of tailored action plan (guided by CSM interview prompt) done in collaboration with patients on each visit
- Participants given food/activity journal to track daily diet/exercise and resource packets containing lists of weight-loss apps, local parks, and healthy food substitutes

Common-Sense Model Interview Prompt

Identity	Cause	Consequences	Control/Cure	Timeline
<p>Assessment Prompts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Would you say that you are underweight, normal weight, or overweight at this point in your life? • Have you been overweight before? • Does anyone in your family have a weight issue? • Do other people comment on your weight? • If you do not feel that you are overweight, is being overweight something that you think about? <p>Action Planning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educate client regarding potential consequences (e.g., cardiovascular risk, metabolic risk, threats to quality of life), timelines (e.g., at what age is loss of mobility most likely, diabetes onset), and risks to gaining additional weight due to medications, lifestyle, eating habits, etc. 	<p>Assessment Prompts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you think can cause you to gain weight? • Why do you think you are overweight? <p>Action Planning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tailor action plan based on client's perceived cause of weight gain • If client believes inactivity is causal, ask client to try and identify ways to increase activity • If client believes unhealthy food choices are causal, refer client to healthy food choices in resource packet; assist client on drawing up shopping list before going to supermarket • If client believes high caloric intake is causal, assist client on planning daily calorie goals using food/activity journal • Can you pick one aspect of your diet or physical activity to work on before we next meet? 	<p>Assessment Prompts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you think your weight is affecting your health? How so? • Do you think your weight will affect your health over the next few years? How? • Do you think your weight is affecting your emotional wellbeing and your relationships with others? How? <p>Action Planning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enrich client's perception of obesity by education about potential consequences • Discuss which consequences matter to client • Ensure that action plan instructs client on how to address experienced consequences or avoid potential consequences 	<p>Assessment Prompts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do you believe that you are in control of your weight? • Have you tried anything to control your weight in the past? • How well did it work? Would you try it again? • Are there any strategies that may help you control your weight? • Are there any resources that would assist you? <p>Action Planning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Help client to identify ways that can control weight • How will you know whether that healthy eating/exercise plan worked? (e.g., weight loss, clothes fit better, rising from chairs more easily) • What do you think is important to do to self-monitor your weight? 	<p>Assessment Prompts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How long have you felt that your weight has been a problem? • Do you perceive that you will be able to control your weight in the future? • How long do you think it will take to change your eating/physical activity habits? <p>Action Planning</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Where and when can that healthy eating/exercise plan fit into your daily schedule? • Help client to set up goals and timeline

Discussion

- Tapping into client common-sense understanding of being overweight is a promising way of motivating clients
- Individualized nature of face-to-face interviews along with provider-patient collaboration in developing a healthy lifestyle plan seems to be key to eliciting behavioral change
- Knowledge of **consequences** was found to be the most motivating factor in starting a healthy lifestyle among participants
- A CSM-based tool can be well-received by mental health clients and be helpful in weight loss efforts

Recommendations

- Discussing weight during mental health visits is integral to address this potentially life-threatening side effect of antipsychotic treatment
- Mental health providers may use the weight management tool kit to help clients lose weight over time, adopt a healthier lifestyle, and encourage them to visit primary care providers to discuss improving other aspects of health

Conclusion

- The weight management tool kit grounded in Leventhal's CSM model can be helpful in fighting antipsychotic-induced obesity
- Implementing a behavioral intervention is feasible in a fast-paced community clinic and is acceptable to patients suffering from mental illness.

Results

- 8 male, 6 female clients.
- Ages 26 to 64 years (mean 44, SD 10.6).
- 43% with Bipolar Disorder, 36% with Schizophrenia, 21% with Schizoaffective Disorder
- At baseline, 21% were overweight, 50% either Obese I or II, 29% extremely obese
- At the third monthly follow-up, average participant weight and BMI changed only slightly (one less person was extremely obese), $F(3) = 8.00, p = .0336$
- 11 of 14 participants lost some weight, and acknowledged that the intervention was helpful

Mean Scores for Tool Helpfulness

Tool	Mean Score (n=13)
Food/Activity Log	~3.5
Resource Packet	~3.5
Healthy Lifestyle Counseling	~4.5

Most Motivating CSM Domain

Domain	Participants
Identity	~1
Cause	~1
Consequences	~10
Controllability	~1
Timeline	~1